

Immunoprophylaxis for Control of Gastrointestinal Parasites of Animals:

From Research to Commercialization

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¹*Research focus: Parasitic vaccines for effective parasitic control

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Abstract

Gastrointestinal (GI) nematodes are considered a significant threat to small ruminant production systems in terms of high morbidity, mortality, production losses, and increased treatment cost. Traditionally, GI parasites are controlled through synthetic chemicals, biological agents, pasture and nutritional management, and selective breeding of parasite-resistant animals. However, all these have limitations in terms of low specificity and sensitivity. Boosting up of host immune system through immunoprophylaxis is a relatively sustainable method. Vaccines successfully control parasitic diseases by utilizing the host's protective immune responsiveness in order to limit the production losses and pathology. Identification of vaccine candidate/proteins antigens against non-blood feeding GI parasites of animals is still a challenge. However, much progress has been made against a model GI parasite of a small ruminant, *Haemonchus (H.) contortus*, a blood-feeding nematode.

Native antigen vaccine against *H.contortus* is effective as up to 75% reduction in fecal egg count has been reported using native antigens as larval ES antigen, cuticular collagens, and other putative antigens. Hidden antigens used against *H.contortus* are H11, H-gal-GP, and Cysteine proteases. Adult 15/24 kDa ES antigens and Hc-sL3 d are recently used native antigens. However, for commercial availability of vaccines, there is a significant need for antigens identification, sequencing of the genome and expressed sequence tag (EST), mRNA expression

analysis, identification of signal sequences, and proteomics. RNA interference for rapid functional screening, Reverse-Transcription PCR, representational difference analysis (RDA), proteomics, and glycomics are molecular technologies used to examine the expression of genes after infection. In order to understand the molecular nature of host-parasite interaction, the use of these biotechnologies would be helpful and may lead to an innovative plan of action for parasite control. A lot of things are under consideration for designing and commercialization of vaccines. The use of vaccination against parasitic diseases of animals in veterinary health services is likely to contribute considerably to aggrandizing the productivity of livestock. Consequently, it is expected that vaccination against parasites will be used as one of the best options to control parasitic infections.

Keywords: Gastrointestinal Parasites, Immunoprophylaxis, Vaccination, Commercialization